

Bioactive Metabolites and Antiquorum Activity of *Nyctanthes Arbor-Tristis* Extracts

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ABSTRACT:

Traditional medicine has played a main role in India. Anti Quorum sensing activity was detected on *Nyctanthes arbor-Tristis* [leaf, flower and stem] extracts and confirmed on by using Pyocyanin quantification assay, Staphylococcal broth activity and Biofilm inhibition assays. The moderate amount of proteins were detected in SDS-PAGE analysis and was observed using silver staining. The FTIR, HPLC analysis showed the presence of compounds like alkaloids, phenols, terpenoids, saponins, flavonoids and glycosides. It also includes Benzoic acid, octadecane, cyclopentane, oleic acid, Tetra decane, pentacosane etc. The GC-MS analysis revealed the presence of 63 natural compounds from the *Nyctanthes arbor-Tristis* [leaf, stem, and flower] extracts. Some of the active compounds include Heneicosane, dodecanoic acid, eicosane Oleic Acid, tetracontane, Cyclopenta, tetradecanoic acid, eicosane, dodecanoic acid etc. The bioactive constituents found in the ethanol extracts of *Nyctanthes arbor-Tristis* [leaf, stem, and flower] could act as the lead compounds, or pharmacological agents. These bioactive metabolites have the possibility to act as molecular targets in the drug development. The prime initiative should focus on the cultivation and conservation of medicinal plants with pharmacological importance.

Keyword: *Anti Quorum, Nyctanthes arbor-Tristis, HPLC, FTIR, GCMS.*

INTRODUCTION

Nyctanthes arbor-tristis Linn. (Oleaceae) is a traditional Indian medicinal plant, commonly called as Night Jasmine (*Pavalamalli* in Tamil) is a small tree growing up to 10 m tall, with flaky grey bark which is widely cultivated throughout India as a garden plant and found wild in the forests of South Indian regions. It is a traditional plant used in the treatment of chronic fevers and rheumatism [1]. The extracted leaf juice along with the sugar acts as a cholagogue, laxative and mild bitter tonic hence given to children as a remedy for intestinal ailments. Potential anti-malarial activity (against malarial fever has also been found associated with *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* Leaves [2]. The medicinal properties of the *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* is extensively used in Ayurveda, Siddha and Unani systems of medicines. Different parts of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* are known to possess medicinal properties for various ailments by tribal people in India. Juice of the leaves is used as digestive, antidote to reptile venoms, laxative, diaphoretic and diuretic [3]. β -Sitosterol isolated from *N. arbor-tristis* leaves showed analgesic and anti-inflammatory activity. Iridoid glucoside isolated from this plant has antileishmanial activity. Ethanolic flower extract of this plant is used for the synthesis of gold nanoparticles. Arbortristoside-A isolated from seeds possesses anti-inflammatory and analgesic activity. Leaf and fruit extracts are useful in the treatment of arthritis. Arbortristoside A and arbortristoside C isolated from plant showed antiviral activity [4]. Ethanol extract of the leaves of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* inhibited acute inflammatory oedema produced by carragenan, formalin, histamine, 5-hydroxytryptamine and hyaluronidase in hind paw of rats. It also reduced acute inflammatory swelling in the knee joint induced by turpentine oil [5]. Methanol extract of leaves of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* exhibited significant hepatoregenerative potential in acetaminophen-induced hepatic damage. It acts by protecting

against membrane fragility and by preventing decline in glutathione levels [6]. The aqueous extracts of the *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* leaves and seeds showed antihepatotoxic activity against CCl₄ induced hepatotoxicity. Similarly ethanol extracts of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* seeds, leaves and flowers caused decreased in the dopamine and increased in serotonin levels. This showed the effect on central nervous system [7].

Aqueous leaf extract of *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* act as a potent immunomodulator of both humoral and cell mediated responses. Seed of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* contains 15% of pale yellow brown oil, nyctanthic acid, nyctoside A, β -sitosterol, arbortristoside A & B, glycerides of linoleic oleic, lignoceric, stearic, palmitic and myristic acids, 3-4 secotriterpene acid and a polysaccharide. It is also composed of D glucose and D mannose which is used as immunostimulant and hepatoprotective [8]. The presence of bioactive metabolites such as polysaccharides, iridoid glycosides, phenylpropanoid glycoside, β -sitosterol, β -amyrin, henti-acontane, benzoic acid, glycosides, nyctanthoside -a iridoid, nyctanthic acid, Friedelin lupeol oleanolic acid and 6 β -hydroxylogananin, iridoid glucosides arbortristoside A, B C, alkaloids, Phlobatanins, terpenoids and cardiac glycosides from the leaf extract of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* [9]. *N. arbor-tristis* flowers yielded iridoid glucosides exhibited antiplasmodial activity against *Plasmodium falciparum*. Besides these compounds, 4-hydroxyhexahydro-benzofuran-7-one nyctoside A, arbortristoside C, arbortristoside D, 6-hydroxylogananin, arbortristoside A, arbortristoside B and nyctanthoside have been reported [10]. The plants used, as drugs are fairly innocuous and relatively free from toxic effects or were so toxic that lethal effects were well known. The nature has provided the storehouse of remedies to cure all ailments of mankind. There is no doubt that plants are a reservoir of potentially useful chemical compounds which serve as drugs, are provided newer leads and clues for modern drug design by

synthesis [11]. The objective of this study is to analyze the bioactive metabolites, and examine the anti quorum activities of *N. arbor-tristis* extracts.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

1. Collection and authentication of plant

The plant *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* was collected from Ayya Nadar Janaki Ammal college campus, Sivakasi, Virudhunagar district, Tamilnadu. The plant *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* (NAT) were washed with water. The Aerial parts (leaf, stem and flower) of the plant was shade dried at 30 °C to 32 °C for 3 days. The dried plants were powdered using motor and pestle and stored in air tight zip lock pouches till extraction.

2. Preparation of extracts

1 g of powdered samples of plant *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* was soaked in 10ml of 70 %ethanol for 5 days. The resultant crude extract was centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 20 minutes and supernatant was collected and evaporated at room temperature (~ 32 °C). The resultant mass was made up to 5 ml using 25% DMSO and used as stock solution (having final concentration of 1 mg/5µl) and stored at 0 °C.

3. Anti Quorum sensing assays

a) Pyocyanin quantification assay

Quantification of Pyocyanin was done as noted by Essar *et al.*, (1990). Overnight culture of *P. aeruginosa* was adjusted to an optical density of 0.2 at 600nm. 250 µl of plant NAT extracts at various concentrations (5µl, 10µl, 20µl, 40µl) was added to 4.75 ml of culture and incubated at 37 °C for 24 hours. The 5 ml culture was extracted with 3 ml of chloroform and 1ml of 0.2 M HCL was added. The absorbance was measured at 520nm..

b) Staphylolytic broth activity

LasA protease activity of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* is determined by the lysis of *Staphylococcus aureus* cells (Kessler *et al.*, 1993). 30ml of *Staphylococcus* broth was boiled for 10minutes and the resultant broth was centrifuged at 10000 rpm for 10minutes. The pellet was resuspended in 10 mMNa₂HPO₄ (pH 7.5) and adjusted to 0.9 at OD 600 nm. A 100µl aliquot of bacterial supernatant was then added to 900µl of *Staphylococcus aureus* suspension and OD at 600 nm was determined after 90 minutes.

c) Biofilm inhibition assay

The effect of plant NAT extracts on the attachment phase of biofilm formation was measured by using the biofilm inhibition assay. Overnight culture of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* was resuspended in nutrient broth in the presence and absence of plant extracts. After 24 hours of incubation period at 30 °C, biofilms were visualized. Plates were rinsed to remove planktonic cells, and surface attached cells were then quantified by solubilizing the dye in ethanol and measuring absorbance at OD 650 nm.

4. FT-IR analysis

The FT-IR analysis of sample was carried for plant extracts (1mg) was taken in a smooth agitate mortar and thoroughly mixed with 2.5 mg of dry potassium bromide (KBr) using a pestle. The powder was filled in the micro cup of 2 mm internal diameter to obtain the diffuse reflectance infrared spectrum for replicate samples. All the IR spectra were recorded at room temperature (26 °c or 10⁰ c) in the mid infrared range (40000.400 cm⁻¹) using FT-IR spectrum RX I, Forier transform infrared spectrometer (perkin Elmer, USA). Typically, 20 scans were signal averaged for a single spectrum. Each spectrum was displayed in terms of absorbance as calculated from the reflectance absorbance spectrum using the Hyper IR software.

5.HPLC analysis

The crude extracts of NAT were quantified by HPLC

SHIMADZU, LC-10 at series machine from the 1.5 ml volume of each crude extracts saved for HPLG CQUANTIFICATION, 200 µl were transferred to a vial and the solvent remove by speed vacuum concentration. The obtained residue was dissolved in 500 µl acetonitrile:water 1:1 +0.5 % trifluoroacetic acid and 10 µl injected by auto sampling into a HPLC. Finally the compounds were analysed based on the retention time.

6. GC-MS analysis

The GC-MS analysis were made using a QP-5000 SHIMADZU, Japan. The 2 µl of NAT extracts was injects into the GC-MS on a 30 m glass capillary column with a film thickness of 0.25µm (30 M x0.2 mm i.d coated with UCON HB 2000) using the following temperature program , initial oven temperature of 40 c or 4 min increased to 250 °C at a rate of 15 °C for 10 min. The gas chromatography (SCHIMADZU GC 15 A) was equipped with FIDM detector connected to an integrator. The area under each peak was used for quantitative calculation. The detection accuracy was about 1 ng/peak. The relative amount of each component was prepared as the percent of the ion current. The GC-MS was under the computer control at 70 ev using ammonia as reagent gas 95ev performed chemical ionization. Identification of unknown compounds was made by probability based matching using the computer library build with the NICT 12 system.

7. SDS PAGE analysis

The further protein profile and the presence of enzyme were confirmed by SDS-PAGE analysis. The separating gel was prepared and mixed well then poured carefully without introducing any air bubbles in between the plates. Allow the plates undisturbed for polymerization of the gel. The water over layer drained out. The degassed stacking gel was prepared then poured over the polymerized separating gel. Immediately the comb inserted on to the polymerization occurs. Now comb was carefully removed and the surface of the well was cleaned with glass distilled water. The sample with the required protein contain is taken and with equal volume of 1X sample buffer (or of the volume of 2X sample buffer) in sterile microfuge tubes and boiled for 3 minutes in a boiling water bath. It was cooled at temperature and then used for loading. If precipitation is observed the samples are microfuged and then for loading. The power was turned on initially with 50 v(15 Mm). Once the tracking dye reach the bottom of the gel, the current was turned off and the gel was taken for staining procedure. The gel was observed using Silver staining method.

4. RESULTS

Figure 1. *Nyctanthes arbor tristis*

Figure 2 shows the pyocyanin production inhibited due to the action of extracts of *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* leaf, stem and flower

using inhibition assay. The absorbance was measured OD at 600 nm. The concentrations of 2.19% *Nyctanthes* stem extract act as the most effective inhibition in the production of pyocyanin is seen. Figure 3 resulted the Las A protease production which was inhibited by the *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* leaf, stem and flower extracts using Staphylolytic Las A protease assay. The absorbance was measured OD at 600nm. Here more effect was observed in the *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* leaf extract at 0.68%. Figure 4 shows that in *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* the biofilm formation was inhibited due to the *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* leaf, stem and flower extracts were seen using the biofilm inhibition assay. The absorbance was measured OD at 650nm. In minimum concentration it is inhibited to 0.30% of *Nyctanthes* flower and maximum concentration it is inhibited to 0.80% of *Nyctanthes* stem. Figure 5a reviews the FT-IR spectrum of *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* leaf. It was measured at 400-4000nm. The FT-IR spectrum of *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* flower was shown in figure 5b. Figure 5c represents the FT-IR spectrum of *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* stem. It was observed that various aliphatic and aromatic compounds are seen in it. Figure 6a analyses the HPLC analysis of the plant derived compounds from the *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* flower extracts. Highest peak denotes the presence of active compounds at the retention time of in *Nyctanthes arbor tristis*. Figure 6b states the HPLC analysis for the *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* leaf. Highest peak denotes the presence of active compounds at the retention time of in *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* leaf. Figure 6c represents the HPLC analysis for the *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* stem extracts. Here the highest peak denotes the presence of active compounds at the retention time of in *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* stem. Figure 7a explains the GC-MS analysis of the *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* leaf extracts.. Based on the relative abundance and time various compounds were observed. 21 compounds are seen in *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* leaf. Figure 7b represents the GC-MS analysis of the *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* flower. 21compounds are seen in *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* flower. Figure 7c reviews the GC-MS analysis of the *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* stem extracts. 21compounds are seen in *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* stem. They are observed based on their molecular weight. Figure 8 represents the protein profile of *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* leaf, flower and stem. They were identified using SDS- PAGE analysis. The molecular weight of the protein at 27kDa was observed. It was compared with standard Bovine serum albumin.

Figure 2: Comparison of pyocyanin production using *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* extract

Figure 3: Comparison of Las A protease activity by using *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* extracts.

Figure 4: Percentage inhibition of biofilm formation in *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* by ethanolic extracts of *Nyctanthes arbor tristis*

Figure 5(a): FTIR analysis of *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* leaf extract

Figure 5(b): FTIR analysis of *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* flower extract

Figure 5(c) : FTIR analysis of *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* stem extract

Figure 6(a): HPLC analysis of *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* flower extract

Figure 6(b): HPLC analysis of *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* leaf extract

Figure 6(c) : HPLC analysis of *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* stem extract

Figure 7a : GC-MS analysis of *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* leaf extract

Figure 7b : GC-MS analysis of *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* flower extract

extract

Figure 7c: GC-MS analysis of *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* stem extract

Figure 8 : SDS PAGE analysis of *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* using silver staining method

4. DISCUSSION

The present observations reveals the bioactive metabolites and anti quorum activities of *Nyctanthes arbor tristis*. Previous report indicates that GC-MS analysis was used to identify the phenolic compounds such as catechol, vanillin, salicylic acid, cinnamic acid, *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid, 2,5-dihydroxybenzoic acid (gentisic acid), syringic acid, *p*-coumaric acid, gallic acid, and *t*-ferulic acid and reported that methanol extract of *Crocus sativus* as carried out by gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS), it contain the silylation by N-methyl-N-trimethylsilyl trifluoroacetamide (MSTFA) + %1 trimethyl iodasilane (TMIS) and also detected the Numerous compounds were detected and 11 compounds were identified [14]. In the present study *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* extract of leaf, stem and flower analyzed the volatile compounds such as 1'-hydroxy-4,3'-dimethyl-bicyclohexyl-3,3'-dien-2-one were present in *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* extract of flower. And n-Dodecanoic acid, Laurostearic acid the compound analyzed from *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* extract of leaf. phenol, 2,4-BIS(1,1-dimethylethyl)-, 2,4-ditert-butylphenol , 1-hydroxy-2, 4-di-tert-butylbenzen were identified from the *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* stem extract. These compounds could be considered as bioactive compounds. Similarly in HPLC analysis chromatogram the compounds seen in *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* leaf stem and flower extracts were detected. Based on the wavelength and

retention time the compounds were analyzed. *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* leaf have broad range is 2.167 were peak formed in retention time. The compound could be octadecane. In flower extracts show the retention time maximum at 1.460 could indicate the presence of Octadecanoic acid. Then in stem at retention time 2.167 the compound be hexadecane. Previous studies stated that methanol extract of *Syzygium cumini* leaves extract chromatogram shows different constituents at various retention times (1.5833, 2.4333). The two peaks are represents the main constituents present in the plant leaves. And another methanol extract of *Eucalyptus* leaves show the various constituents with different retention times (2.5500, 3.1393, 3.5000, 4.9000, 5.6333, and 7.0000) [15]. It was demonstrated the *polyalthia longifolia* extract IR absorption showed below 1000 cm^{-1} corresponded to C-H bending attributes the stretching vibration of C-O of monosaccharids, oligosaccharids and carbohydrates [16]. The *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* leaf extract showed broad band 3379.05 cm^{-1} , the minimum band were 1114.78 cm^{-1} , and the middle band were denoted by 1733.89 cm^{-1} . The *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* flower extract showed broad band 3377.12 cm^{-1} and minute band were 1114.78 cm^{-1} and the middle band at 2075.26 cm^{-1} . The *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* stem extract showed broad band 3377.12 cm^{-1} , the minute band were 1114.78 cm^{-1} and the middle band were 1735.81 cm^{-1} .

It was noted that the most of the Indian spices like *side acuta* and *Gomphrena serrata* have control the quenches of bacterial signaling and Pyocyanin production. The active ingredients in the *side acuta* and *Gomphrena serrata* extract of flower might be a type of competitive inhibitor in contrast with active ingredient of leaf extract of *side acuta* and *Gomphrena serrata* which is not so. So as the concentration of the extract increases it competitively inhibits the pyocyanin production more over effectively than others. The presence of biological active components such as, flavonoids, saponin, terpenoids and phenol compounds in the extracts of flower *side acuta* and *Gomphrena serrata* were seen. These biological active compounds at lower concentration depicts the lower inhibition of activity was reported [17]. In the present study the *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* have the ability reduce the Pyocyanin production and showed the property of anti quorum sensing. Because the bioactive compounds, such as flavonoids, saponins and Cardiac glycosides etc more over present in the *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* extract were compared with *side acuta* and *Gomphrena serrata* [18]. The quorum quenching activity of biofilm formation *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* at range various from 1.78% to 70.12% by the extract of *Urena lobata*. Then the interference is mainly attributed to the secondary metabolites of inhibit the biofilm formation, because there are some cases with low secondary metabolite profile with maximum biological activity against biofilm formation [19]. *Melicope lunu ankenda* extract was used as anti quorum sensing which was analyzed thoroughly by to compare the phytochemical status with the biofilm inhibition in the *Chromobacterium violaceum* [20].

Presently anti quorum sensing was detected in *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* extracts against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* at 600nm. The biofilm formation was inhibited due the potency of the extracts. The *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* leaves of phytochemical profile is average but its most effective in both controlling the inhibit the biofilm formation of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and scavenging free radicals at range from 0.40% to 0.80% to inhibit the biofilm production. The *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* leaf, stem and flower inhibited the production of pyocyanin and Las A production. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* was used in it. Previous study revealed that *staphylolytic* Las A production was inhibited

from *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* using extract of *malachra capitata* leaf and stem. He stated that pyocyanin inhibition in the extract of clove. With all the plant extracts a good level of inhibition was observed and showed the presence of multiple quorum sensing inhibiting compounds saponin, flavonoid, tepenoid etc. present at different quantities of the plant [21]. In this study of *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* leaf, stem and flower extract to inhibit the Las A production, the high range of 0.68% the extraction of *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* leaf extract compare then other stem and flower extract of *Nyctanthes arbor tristis*. The present data suggests that bacterial intercellular communication, or quorum sensing (QS), controls the pathogenesis of many medically important organisms. Anti-QS compounds have the ability to attenuate bacterial pathogenicity. The determination of minimum QS inhibition concentration towards *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* extracts by using *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* was the interesting idea. Preliminary screening was implemented to determine whether the anti-Quorum sensing compounds were actually from the plants themselves. Quorum sensing (QS) is a widespread prokaryotic intercellular communication system based on the signal molecules (autoinducers) relative to cell density. Compounds that interfere with the QS system to attenuate bacterial pathogenicity are termed as anti-QS compounds [22]. The present work demonstrates that availability of proteins in the extract of *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* leaf, stem and flower. Present studies using GC-MS analysis revealed that 63 active bioactive metabolites are analyzed. Some of the active compounds include Heneicosane, dodecanoic acid, eicosane Oleic Acid, tetracontane, Cyclopenta, tetradecanoic acid, eicosane, dodecanoic acid etc. Based on GC-MS analysis various chemical constituents are reported in *Centella asiatica* like asiaticoside, madecassoside, madecassic acid, asiatic acid, glucose, rhamnose, terpenoids, sitosterol, stigmasterol, fatty oils consist of glycerides of palmitic acid, stearic acid, linoleic acid, linolenic acid vitamins like ascorbic acid [23]. The protein bands were observed from *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* leaf, stem and flower extracts and were visualized in silver staining method, because the low molecular weight of protein separate only in the silver staining. The *Nyctantes arbor tristis* leaf extract had high content of proteins when compared with that of stem and flower. Coomassie Brilliant were using the identification of high molecular weight of protein bands, but *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* leaf sample have low molecular weight so the protein bands were observed through the silver staining method. And the protein universal high molecular marker weight 205 kDa and use the low molecular weight 29 kDa was used. The present study helps to predict the availability of bioactive metabolites. Further investigation could lead to the isolation of bio-active compounds their structural elucidation and screening of pure compounds will be helpful for further drug development.

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